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Extent Of Effectiveness In Classroom Management Of Post Graduate Diploma In Education (PGDE) Graduates In Secondary Schools In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study was on the effectiveness in classroom management of Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) in secondary schools in Delta State. The main purpose of this study was to investigate the extent of effectiveness in classroom management of graduates of PGDE in secondary schools in Delta State. Three (3) research questions will guide the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study was nine hundred and fifty-eight (958) approved public secondary school principals and one hundred and thirty eight (138) approved private secondary school principals in Delta state. Sample size for the study was two hundred and eighty-seven (287) public and private secondary school principals who were selected through proportionate random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled “Extent of Effectiveness in Classroom Management of Post Graduate Diploma in Education Graduates in secondary schools in Delta State (EECMPGDEG)” consisting of fifteen (15) items spread across four clusters and structured in four points rating scale. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, the internal consistency of the instrument was computed using Cronbach Alpha. The overall reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.82. The data was collected and analyzed using mean to answer the research questions. The study revealed that PGDE graduates’ effectiveness in teaching pedagogy in lesson presentation, reporting with students and evaluating students is to a low extent. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made among others: Educational planners should make effective set up on increasing the duration of PGDE programme, Directors of the PGDE program should emphasize practical classroom experience more than the theoretical knowledge by incorporating not just teaching practicums which is usually very short but also mentorship opportunities under the guidance of experienced educators and Teacher Educators should participate in the selection process of PGDE trainees through preparation of instruments that can help identify suitable candidates with strong commitment to the teaching profession.

Keywords: Classroom Management; PGDE; Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Post graduate diploma in education is the indispensable graduate study program that can make the unqualified personnel qualified in teaching profession. In the light of this, Abdurahman, Mohammed and Khaled (2022) viewed Post graduate diploma in education as a post graduate program for holders of the Higher National Diploma (HND) and Degrees (B.A, BSc, MSc, PhD) who wish to be teachers but do not possess teaching qualification required to be registered with Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria. PGDE programme is therefore specially mapped out to train interested graduates in

various fields who wish to take up teaching as a profession on child psychology, theories of learning, teaching methodology and general principles and practice of education so as to be equipped with the skills of teaching. The programme is scrutinized by the board of teachers registration council whose membership include among others, NUC, NCCE, NUT, NBTE and Nigerian Academy of Education. Many students over the years have studied courses other than education, thereby acquiring degree certificates in other disciplines.

Most of these students choose a career in teaching profession without professional teaching qualification, hence the observation of Uche and Augustine (2016) that over 60 percent of teachers in public primary and secondary schools in Nigeria are unqualified because they have no professional certificate in education. In Nigeria, reasonable preparations are made to improve teachers' professional development through the establishment of colleges of education, both at the federal and state levels. Institutes of education and faculties of education in various universities are also established to provide effective and professional teacher education programs. In such institutions, students are trained to form habits that will help them become teachers capable of shouldering responsibilities, showing initiative and being good models for their future pupils and students. This is because an incompetent teacher is a disgrace to the teaching profession. Incompetence in teaching according to Demis, Haileslasie & Dawit (2015) may be a matter of low intellectual capacity, inadequate training, and resistance to modern pedagogical methods, or poor attitude about the teaching profession and a lack of dedication to professional duties. Demis, Haileslasie & Dawit opined that the PGDE Programme is theoretical and practical and includes important aspects of teaching and learning.

The programme addresses the philosophical problems of the bases of educational practice, the diverse human settings within which teaching and learning occur, the practical process, content of teaching and the definition of the teacher's role and teaching ethics. At the end of the programme, learners should have in-depth knowledge of education and the professional requirements as well as competence to adequately teach at various levels of education including secondary schools. Interested teachers without professional teaching certificates therefore register for PGDE programme in order to acquire necessary teaching skills to be qualified to take up teaching duties at different levels of the education system (Nursery, Basic, Senior Secondary and Tertiary levels), or to assume leadership position in any education organization or agency. Some of these PGDE graduates are in secondary schools, hence the researchers interests in finding out the extent of their effectiveness in classroom management as teachers in their various schools.

Effectiveness in performance can be referred to as the results of activities of an individual or organization over a given period of time or the assessment of how well a task is being done. Dejene (2020) defined teachers' effectiveness as the observable or measurable behaviour of a teacher in a particular situation usually experimental situation. This implies that the observed behavior of an individual must be measured or tested at a given period of time to determine his/her effectiveness. Effectiveness is therefore determined by carrying out test which can either be mentally, orally or at best practically. Effectiveness in performance therefore refers to achievement in carrying out of a task, assignment or course allocated to one. In this study, effectiveness test in performance would be carried out on graduates of PGDE in classroom management in the various secondary schools in Delta state where they teach.

The classroom could be seen as a school environment which accommodates teachers, pupils, instructional materials and infrastructure facilities which enable teaching and learning experience or problems to take place. Hence, Ogor and Ofuani (2024). viewed classroom as the school environment where learning takes place. This learning experience in the classroom cannot take place without good management. Onyema (2019) opined that Management involves the coordination of all resources of an organization through the process of planning organizing, directing and controlling in order to attain organizational objectives. Classroom experience should therefore be managed. Iloh, Ezugoh, Ogor and Okonta (2022) defined Classroom management as effective utilization of available resources in the classroom for the accomplishment of stated objectives and to make resource productive in order that the teaching and learning process may achieve its goals. It is also concerns with the organization of non-academic task such as checking of class attendance, record keeping of class progress, monitoring and regulating the activities and behavior of students maintaining order which are essential for teaching and learning. To this end, good or effective classroom management

can be viewed as the key to success of teaching and learning, hence any PGDE graduate is expected to be effective in classroom management.

There is no human endeavour that does not require proper management for its proper functioning. All types of organization, government establishments, business enterprises, hospitals, schools, cooperatives, churches among others require good management to function effectively. The concept of management has been variously defined. Okoh and Ogogor (2024) opined that management can simply be defined as getting things done through the help of resources, which can be human or material. So, in education, management could be perceived as using human or material resources to carry out educational functions. In addition, Iloh, Nwaham, Igbinedion and Ogogor (2016) perceived management in education as the effective and efficient utilization of both human and material resources to achieve specified educational goals. This shows that classroom management has to do with the impact of the teacher in classroom activities. Ogogor and Ofuani (2024) asserted that although the teachers play various roles in a typical classroom, the most important is that of classroom manager which the teacher does through lesson presentation, rapport with students, classroom organization and lesson evaluation. Thus, these are the key areas of teachers' classroom management that can form bases of assessing the effectiveness of PGDE graduates in their various schools of assignment. These key areas of classroom management include:

Lesson Presentation

In the school system, there are many students under the classroom teacher. The teacher has to utilize all available avenues to manage these students including presenting his lesson well. Lesson presentation is the manner lessons are handed down to students. This involves the teacher using all available strategies to ensure that teaching and learning is efficient and effective. Iloh, Onyema, Morrison, Okonta and Maha (2020) says that the lesson presentation requires pre-classroom preparation and activities by the teacher which he has to put in their proper places before presenting himself in the classroom. To Iloh, Onyema, Morrison, Okonta and Maha, these teacher's preparation or activities should include the following: Planning the course contents, planning the resources and planning the lesson. This shows that failure to plan is planning to fail in lesson presentation. This is because lesson plan helps the teacher to execute and implement the lesson effectively with fewer mistakes.

Effective lesson presentation requires instructional materials. These materials are said to provide means by which teachers present their lessons effectively. Iloh, Onyema, Morrison, Okonta and Maha (2020) also identified books and other educational materials as the basic tools of lesson presentation. Such materials must therefore be available to the teacher and learner in adequate quality and quantities and must also be available at the time they are required. When a teacher provides inspiration for learning, the teaching presentation will be easy and comfortable. This study therefore intends to find out the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates even in lesson presentation.

Rapport with student

Teacher-student rapport can be conceptualized as an emotional connection between teachers and their students based on understanding, caring, and mutual respect. Culpeper and Kan (2020) noted that teacher-student rapport is a close bond between instructors and learners that enables them to work jointly in classroom contexts. Therefore, a positive and favorable relationship between teachers and students is called teacher-student rapport. Reyes and Von Anthony (2020) defined this construct as "a harmonious teacher-student relationship which encompasses enjoyment, connection, respect, and mutual trust". Valuing students' ideas and viewpoints is a key to build a strong rapport with them. In this regard, Reyes and Von Anthony postulated that demonstrating concern for students' welfare is also essential for establishing a positive relationship with them. Taken together, those teachers who respect students' ideas and pay attention to their well-being are able to develop a strong connection with their students. Building rapport in classrooms is of high importance, mostly due to the fact that having close relationships with students motivates them to collaborate with teachers in order to attain their mutual objectives.

In classroom interactions, teachers and students may influence each other either positively or negatively. A negative teacher-student relationship may lead to stress, anxiety, and aggression in students. Accordingly, creating a positive relationship with students is among the top priorities of teachers in any educational setting. To establish rapport in classrooms, graduates of PGDE should be

able to pay attention to students' interests, value their beliefs and ideas, and allow them to freely express their feelings toward classroom instruction.

In addition, Frisby (2017) opined that having a sense of humor and providing continuous feedback are also enumerated as the approaches through which teachers can create a close relationship with their students. To illuminate the significance of teacher-student rapport, Ibarra (2014) stated that the strong rapport between teachers and students can contribute to desirable academic performance. In this regard, Nathan (2018) postulated that those teachers who are able to build a harmonious relationship with their students can effectively improve their sense of accomplishment; this study therefore intends to find out the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in creating good classroom rapport with their students.

Teachers' Lesson Evaluation

"Evaluation" doesn't always correspond to "testing." Evaluation can and should be carried out both during and after instruction. It may be both formal and informal. Formal evaluation is done after instruction to confirm whether the teacher and students have successfully accomplished the objectives of what is taught. Ogogor and Ofuani (2024) stated that Formal evaluation involves creating or selecting an appropriate language test and then administering, scoring, and interpreting it

Evaluation plays an enormous role in the teaching-learning process. It helps teachers and learners to improve teaching and learning. Evaluation is a continuous process and a periodic exercise. Evaluation helps in forming the values of judgment, educational status, or achievement of student. It is in one form or the other inevitable in teaching and learning, as in all other fields of activity because judgments or assessment need to be made on activities performed. The activities of both the teacher and learners need constant assessment to ascertain progress so far made. Activities that are not evaluated may be fruitless and baseless. Everyone is usually encouraged by results. Any competent teacher should be able to evaluate all activities, available resources, instructional methodologies and teaching-learning process and feedback given to students. Therefore, one way to test the effectiveness of PGDE graduates effectiveness and performance is in their ability to carry out evaluation very effectively.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers stand out as one of the most important factors determining the quality of education in any country. There has been a general conception in Nigeria among teaching and nonteaching staff that the ability to teach with enthusiasm may be both in-born and acquired. It is further argued that a period of professional training may not make much difference as long as one has academic qualification. Hence, the public see intelligence, interest, and other personal traits as the only qualities assumed to be necessary for effective teaching. Therefore, not all practicing teachers are professionally trained, hence the emergence of Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) which is focused on training teachers to be professionals in teaching. Notwithstanding, the effect of the PGDE programme on the knowledge, attitude, behaviour and skills of graduates of PGDE seem to be in contention, especially with the notion and common criticism against the PGDE programme that it is a crash programme. Therefore, there is cause to doubt its effectiveness on its graduates. It is against this backdrop that the researchers wish to assess Post graduate diploma in education (PGDE) graduates to find out the extent of their effectiveness in their classroom management performance in different secondary schools where they teach in Delta state.

Goals and Objectives

The main objective of this study is to investigate the extent of effectiveness in classroom management of graduates of PGDE in secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study will seek to:

1. Ascertain the extent of effectiveness in lesson presentation of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State.
2. Determine the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates' rapport with students in secondary schools in Delta State.
3. Access the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in lesson evaluation in secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. What is the extent of effectiveness in lesson presentation of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State?

2. What is the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates' rapport with students in secondary schools in Delta State?
3. What is the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in lesson evaluation in manifesting self-efficacy in secondary schools in Delta State?

METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for the study was descriptive survey design. A sample of the large population was studied, and the data analyzed without manipulation. The population of the study was nine hundred and fifty eight (958) approved public secondary school principals and one hundred and thirty eight (138) approved private secondary school principals in Delta state. Sample size for the study was two hundred and eighty seven (287) public and private secondary school principals representing 30% of the entire population, who were selected through proportionate random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Extent of Effectiveness in Classroom Management of Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) Graduates in secondary schools in Delta State (EECMPGDEG)" The instrument consisted fifteen (15) items spread across four clusters and structured in four points rating scale. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, the internal consistency of the instrument was computed using Cronbach Alpha. The overall reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.82 showing that the questionnaire was reliable. Out of two hundred and eighty seven (287) questionnaires distributed, two hundred and fifty three (253) were returned. Data collected was represented in tables and analyzed using mean score at 2.50 rating.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

Research Question 1: *What is the extent of effectiveness in lesson presentation of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 1: The extent of effectiveness in lesson presentation of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
	PGDE graduates:		
1	Use instructional materials effectively	2.28	LE
2	Have good communication with their students	2.64	HE
3	Have their lessons well and sequentially presented	2.32	LE
4	Have good classroom organization	2.22	LE
5	Have well written lesson plan/notes	2.34	LE
Grand Mean		2.36	

Analysis on Table 1 shows mean scores on the extent of effectiveness in lesson presentation of PGDE graduates in secondary schools in Delta State. The analyses revealed that the respondents rated all items below a mean score of 2.50 except item 2 which has the mean score of 2.64. The grand mean of 2.36 which is below 2.50 also implies that principals' view of effectiveness in lesson presentation of PGDE graduate teachers was to low extent. However, item 2 with mean score above 2.50 indicated that PGDE graduate teachers have good communication with the students.

Research Question 2: *What is the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates' rapport with students in secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 2: The extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates' rapport with students in secondary schools in Delta State.

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
	PGDE graduate teachers:		
6	Use praise and reward	2.56	HE
7	Have harmonious teacher/students relationship	2.41	LE
8	Have good classroom control	2.53	HE
9	Are compassionate with students welfare	1.88	LE
10	Are easily angry and aggressive with students	2.87	HE
Grand Mean		2.45	

Table 2 reveals mean scores on the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates' rapport with students in secondary schools in Delta State. The results in this table indicated that the responses to items 6 and 8 showed high extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates' teachers' rapport with students with mean scores of 2.56, 2.53. However, the mean scores of items 7, 9 and 10 indicated a low extent level of rapport of PGDE graduate teachers with students. Note that item 10 though it has a mean score of 2.87 indicated low level of rapport with students. The grand mean of 2.45 which is below 2.50 also showed that the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates' rapport with students in secondary schools in Delta State was to a low extent. However, items 6 and 8 from their mean scores indicated that PGDE graduate teachers use praise and reward and have good class control to a high extent.

Research Question 3: *Access the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in lesson evaluation in secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 3: The extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in lesson evaluation in secondary schools in Delta State.

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
	PGDE graduate teachers:		
11	Are eager to give tests and assignments	2.24	LE
12	Elicit feedback from students to monitor their progress	2.17	LE
13	Carry out progressive evaluation and assessment	2.25	LE
14	Keep poor records	2.41	LE
15	Are prompt in marking students' assignments and tests	2.38	LE
Grand Mean		2.29	

Data analyzed on Table 3 showed the mean scores of the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in lesson evaluation in secondary schools in Delta State. Table 3 indicated that the respondents rated all the items below the mean score of 2.50. This implies that the extent of effectiveness of PGDE graduates in lesson evaluation in secondary schools in Delta State is to a low extent.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study in the first research question revealed low extent of effectiveness in lesson presentation of PGDE graduate teachers in secondary schools in Delta State. The result showed that post graduate diploma in education graduate teachers' effective use of instructional material, sequential lesson presentation, good classroom organization and well written lesson plan are all to a low extent of effectiveness. This seems to align with the findings of Emmanuel, Iormough, Fiase, Achukwu, and Chia (2017) who reported that PGDE graduates seem not to have learnt enough professional competence in their short term program which limits their ability to acquire the skills relevant for teaching. Wali and Uwah (2025) in their study however acknowledged that PGDE graduates demonstrated improved lesson planning and delivery but also observed that some of the graduates lacked depth in pedagogical content knowledge. The study therefore affirms that PGDE enhance lesson presentation skills but also stressed the importance of practical experience and ongoing professional development to maximize teaching effectiveness.

The result of the second research question revealed low extent effectiveness of PGDE graduates' rapport with students in secondary schools in Delta State. From the result, it is deduced that PGDE graduate teachers have low extent of effectiveness in harmonious teacher/students relationship, compassion with students' welfare and high extent in being easily angry and aggressive with students. These sum up to the fact of low extent effectiveness in their rapport with students. Wali and Uwah (2025) supports this finding by laying emphasis on educational psychology and communication skills which contribute to improved teacher-student relationship. Concurring to this, Itedjere (2025) observed that PGDE graduate teachers need emotional intelligence and reflective practice to help them connect better with students. Itedjere recommended mentorship and peer coaching to be integrated into PGDE programs to sustain rapport building.

The last table showed the result of the findings in result question three which revealed that effectiveness of PGDE graduates in lesson evaluation in secondary schools in Delta State is to a low

extent. From the responses, PGDE graduate teachers' eagerness to assess the students, progressive evaluation, feedback from students' assessment and record keeping are all to a low level of effectiveness. This findings seem to be summed up in Befekadu (2021) observation that PGDE trainees had an unfavourable attitude towards teaching pointing out that a large number of the trainees joined the teaching profession only due to a lack of other job opportunities. However, the findings contradicted Abdurahman , Mohammed and Khaled (2022) findings on students perception on teaching effectiveness of PGDE graduates which was reported to be very positive particularly in providing adequate subject matter knowledge and in employing several assessment techniques. In addition, Ige (2024) found out that PGDE graduate teachers were found to be competent in summative evaluation but less confident in diagnostic and formative assessments stressing the need for continuous professional development to enhance evaluative effectiveness. Hence Ige maintained that PGDE alone is not sufficient stressing that continuous training and mentorship are essential for sustained effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

The study has investigated on the extent of effectiveness in classroom management of graduates of PGDE in secondary schools in Delta State. Key findings indicated that though PGDE graduate teachers have good class control and communication with their students, they have low extent of effectiveness in teaching pedagogy in lesson presentation, reporting with students and evaluating students. This may be attributed to lack of interest in the teaching profession, lack of professional follow up training after the program which has very short duration. However, a careful adjustment in relevant places will produce the best of teachers from the program.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Educational Administrators should investigate the feedbacks from both teachers and students regarding the effectiveness of PGDE. This can yield valuable insight and help in refining the PGDE curricular.
2. Directors of the PGDE program should emphasize practical classroom experience more than the theoretical knowledge by incorporating not just teaching practicums which is usually very short but also mentorship opportunities under the guidance of experienced educators.
3. Teacher Educators should participate in the selection process of PGDE trainees through preparation of instruments that can help identify suitable candidates with strong commitment to the teaching profession
4. Graduates of PGDE should be provided with follow up trainings through collaboration
5. Educational planners should make effective set up on increasing the duration of PGDE programme.

REFERENCES

- Abdurahman A. E., Mohammed H. S. & Khaled A. A. (2022). Teaching Effectiveness of Postgraduate Diploma in Teaching and Integrated Curriculum Graduate Teachers: Investigating Students' and Teachers' Perceptions. *Hindawi Education Research International Journal* 1(1) 2022, 1-6.
- Befekadu, Z (2021). Attitude of Postgraduate Diploma in Teaching (PGDT) trainees towards the teaching profession in Ethiopia. *African Journal of Teachers' Education*. 10 (1), 153-171.
- Culpeper, J., and Kan, Q. (2020). Communicative styles, rapport, and student engagement: An online peer mentoring scheme. *Appl. Linguist*.
- Demis G., Haileslasie, B. & Dawit T. (2015). An Exploration Of Student-Teachers' Views About The Practice Of Postgraduate Diploma In Teaching: English Major Prospective Teachers In Bahir Dar And Haromaya Universities, Ethiopia: *International Journal Of Learning, Teaching And Educational Research*. 13(3)192-209
- Emmanuel O. C., Iormough J. T., Fiase T. M., Achukwu C. E. & Chia T. (2017). Assessment of the Effectiveness of Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) Programme in Meeting the Job Needs of Teachers in Gboko, Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education, Culture and Society*. 2(1)

- Frisby, B. N., and Martin, M. M. (2017). Instructor–student and student–student rapport in the classroom. *Commun. Educ.*
- Ibarra, S. (2014). The Effect of Student-Teacher Rapport on Classroom Participation (*Master's Thesis*). Cardinal Stritch University, Milwaukee, Wisconsin.
- Ige, N. A. (2024) effectiveness of teacher professional development programmes in improving student learning outcome in tertiary institutions in Lagos state Nigeria. *American International Journal of Business Management*, 7 (8), 180-188
- Iloh, C. A., Nwaham, C. O., Igbinedion, J. O. and Ogor, T. N (2016). *Fundamentals of educational administration and supervision*, Agbor: Progress P. E. Printing Associate.
- Iloh, C.A., Ezugoh, T.C., Ogor, T.N. & Okonta, L.I. (2022). *Comprehensive text in educational administration, planning and supervision*. Agbor; Progress P.E. Printing Associates
- Iloh, C. A., Onyema, P. C., Morrison, U., Okonta, I, L, & Maha, O. (2020). *Classroom Management and Organization*. Agbor, Emmy Iyk ventures.
- Itejere, E. F. (2025) exploring the effectiveness of teacher training programs in Nigeria. *Global Educational Research Journal*, 54-61
- Nathan, L. (2018). *Student-Teacher Rapport and Its Impact on Students' Sense of Fulfillment* (Master's Thesis). California State University, Monterey Bay.
- Ogor, T. N & Ofuani, R. O. (2024). Principals' Perception of Teachers' Competence in Classroom Management in Secondary Schools in Oshimili South Local Government Area, Delta State. *Journal of Education, the Teacher and Professional Practices*, 2(2), 588-600.
- Okoh, P.A. & Ogor, T. N. (2024). Management of Home economics education for sustainable national development in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Review of African Educational Studies*. Vol 2 (1).
- Onyema, P.C (2019). *Introduction to Issues on Sociology of Education*. Enugu; Chambus Communication
- Reyes, R. D. G. D., and Von Anthony, G. T. (2020). The relationship of expert teacher–learner rapport and learner autonomy in the CVIF dynamic learning program. *Asia-Pacific Educ. Res.*
- Uche, C. M. & Augustine, S. E.(2016) Relevance of post graduate diploma in education program to students in furthering their education: A case study of University of Port-Harcourt. *Journal of Educatiinal Research and Review*. 3(5), 76-85.
- Wali, C. F. & Uwah, I. V. (2025) Evaluation of post graduate diploma in education (PGDE) programs in University of PortHarcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education Research*, 11(1), 42-53.